

Science with INTEGRAL

... How it started ...

... How it ended ...

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ESOC, 17 – 21 October 2022

*This is NOT a review talk „20 years of INTEGRAL Science“
but rather a „Elder-scientist-non-expert-talk“*

The last Century ... in 1985 ...

- Michail Gorbatschow: General Secretary of Soviet Communist Party
- Discovery of the wreck “Titanic“
- Maiden Flight Space Shuttle Atlantis
- Launch of „Giotto“ to Comet Halley
- Presentation of Windows 1.0.1
- E-mail did not exist
- 1. January 1985: my first working day @ Estec

Planned/active missions 40 years ago

V. Schönfelder & J. Greiner, 2021

The Compton Gamma-Ray Observatory

Hard keV/soft MeV range:

- Imaging $\approx 1\text{-}4$ deg
- Spectroscopy $\Delta E/E \approx 10\%$ (NaI)
- Large NaI detectors
- Launch: 1991*
- Re-entry: 2000

* Delay due to Challenger Disaster 1986

Comptel: MPE/SRON/Estec/UNH

SIGMA/Granat

Hard keV/soft MeV range:

- Imaging \approx arcmin
- Spectroscopy $\approx \Delta E/E \approx 10\%$
- Large NaI detector
- Launch: 1989
- Re-entry: 1999

CESR, CE Saclay, IKI

July 1985: ESA Call for New Mission Proposals

The need to combine **arcminute imaging** with **high-resolution spectroscopy** in the hard keV to few MeV energy range

Key instrument features:

- **Coded Aperture Mask**
- **Cooled Ge-detectors**
- **Pixellated detector arrays**

Submission of the „GRASP mission proposal“ by A. J. Dean representing a large international collaboration.

GRASP = Gamma-Ray Astronomy with Spectroscopy and Positioning

The GRASP/NAE merger

- GRASP was **not** selected by ESA (> Huygens/Cassini, CGRO launch pending)
- NAE (**N**uclear **A**strophysics **E**xplorer) was **not** selected by NASA
- Both teams (Euro & US) joined forces and A.J. Dean and J.L. Matteson et al. submitted the **INTEGRAL** proposal in response to ESA's next Call for New Missions in 1989
- INTEGRAL = **I**nternational **G**amma-**R**ay **A**strophysics **L**aboratory
- **Selection** as ESA's new medium-size mission (M2) in **1993**
- Phase-A report („The red book“), Programme Schedule, p.90:
 - **Launch: Spring 2001 planned** (→ *Fall 2002*)
 - **End ops: Spring 2005 planned** (→ *Spring 2023 .. ? 2029 ?*)

Integral: a “horizon 2000” child

- INTEGRAL = “medium-size mission” (M2) in Horizon 2000 long-term plan
- Collaboration with Russia and NASA
- ❖ Russian launch vehicle
- ❖ XMM-Newton service module
- ❖ Science data centre/archive

Imaging

Comptel/CGRO view of the galactic anti-centre region

5 deg

Sigma/Granat view of Nova Muscae

2 deg

INTEGRAL view of GC region

2 deg

Spectroscopy

NaI(Tl), $\Delta E/E$ @ 511 keV $\sim 7\% = 35$ keV
OSSE/CGRO

Ge (HP), $\Delta E/E$ @ 511 keV $\sim 0.5\% = 2.5$ keV
INTEGRAL/SPI

Outline Mission Objectives

- Compact Objects
 - White Dwarfs.....cataclysmic variables
 - Neutron stars.....isolated & in binaries
 - Black Hole candidates
- Stellar Nucleosynthesis
 - Hydrostatic.....stellar evolution
 - Supernovae.....historical & present
 - Novae.....historical & present
- Transient sources
 - Gamma-ray bursts
 - Gamma-ray transient sources
- Source Identification
- Unidentified gamma-ray objects as a class
- The Structure of the Galaxy
 - Cloud Complex Regions
 - Galactic mapping of continuum and line emissions
 - Interstellar gasses and dust
 - Cosmic and sub-Cosmic Ray Distributions
- Particle Processes and Acceleration
- Transrelativistic Pair Plasmas
- The Galactic centre
- Extragalactic Astronomy
 - Nearby Galaxies
 - Clusters of Galaxies
 - Active Galactic Nuclei
 - Cosmic Diffuse Background

PLUS - Unexpected discoveries

*INTEGRAL 1993 Science Case
Presentation, A.J. Dean et al.*

17.10. – 21.10. 2022

INTEGRAL - 20 years, ESOC

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ISWT on the road to the launch site
Baikonur/Kazachstan, 2002

Excellent Launcher & Excellent Orbit

The Observing Programme (e.g. 2012)

Scheduled Observations Rev 1132 (20 Jan 2012) - Rev 1253 (19 Jan 2013)
25.1 Ms total, 80% efficiency

What was predicted and achieved ?

The Galactic Plane Scans

INTEGRAL GPS scan, revolution 26 (30 Dec 2002)

JEM-X: "new" source/ROSAT transient

XRT/Swift TOO follow-up: precise location and spectrum

M. Focchi et al., 2014

Optical counterpart ID

Galactic HMXB

The transient high energy sky

Sources can appear in ~ 1000 s

Or in few days

Rev 169

Rev 171 (6 days later)

Or in few weeks

GPS, new sources, ToO alert, Catalogues, Distribution of galactic compact objects

F. Lebrun et al., 2004

R. Krivonos et al., 2010

Galactic diffuse emission of the positron/electron annihilation line @ 511 keV

$$E = m \cdot c^2$$

P. Jean et al., 2006

L. Bouchet et al., 2010

Gamma-ray lines from type Ia SN 2014J in M82

Isotope	Lifetime	Decay chain	Gamma-rays [keV]
^{56}Ni	111 days	$^{56}\text{Ni} \rightarrow ^{56}\text{Co} \rightarrow ^{56}\text{Fe}$	847, 1238

Gamma-ray lines from type II SN 1987A in LMC

Isotope	Lifetime	Decay chain	Gamma-rays [keV]
^{44}Ti	98 years	$^{44}\text{Ti} \rightarrow ^{44}\text{Sc} \rightarrow ^{44}\text{Ca}$	68, 78, 1156

IBIS/ISGRI maps of the sky region ($1.5^\circ \times 1.5^\circ$) near SN 1987A in three subsequent energy bands:
48–65, **65–82**, 82–99 keV.

S. Grebenev et al., 2012

Gamma-ray line emission from the Galaxy

Isotope	Lifetime	Decay chain	Gamma-rays [keV]
^{26}Al	10^6 years	$^{26}\text{Al} \rightarrow ^{26}\text{Mg} + e^+$	511, 1809

L. Bouchet et al., 2015

R. Diehl et al., 2006

Galaxy-wide origin of ^{26}Al emission reflects current massive-star population throughout entire Galaxy

Independent method to determine current Galactic core-collapse SN rate and derive star formation rate

Polarized hard X-ray emission in Crab, Cyg X-1 and in GRB 041219a

P. Laurent et al., 2011

Important INTEGRAL Results

The first...

- large-scale sky-map at 511 keV (electron-positron annihilation)
- measurement of the true fraction of Compton-thick AGN
- ever detection of ^{56}Co lines and a continuum from Type Ia SN
- GRB associated with a gravitational event

Discovery of...

- a new class of binaries enshrouded by massive stellar wind (“strongly absorbed HMXB”)
- a new regime of intermittent accretion in wind-fed relativistic binaries (“SFXT”)
- dominance of accreting WD in the “diffuse” galactic ridge hard X-ray emission
- hard spectral tails in extremely magnetized neutron stars: e^\pm pairs dominated fireball
- the most distant QSO seen in hard X-rays
- a population of faint GRB with long spectral lags
- strong flaring activity of microquasar V404 Cyg – source of galactic 511 keV emission ?

Detection of...

- ^{44}Ti lines from SN Cas A and SN 1987 A
- hard X-ray emission from black holes, LMXB, and accreting ms pulsars
- polarized hard X-ray emission in Crab, Cyg X-1 and in GRB 041219a
- cyclotron line strength correlated with the height of the accretion column
- pulsed hard X-ray emission up to ~ 150 keV from rotation-powered pulsars

... and last but not least ...

- proved the Galaxy wide origin of the ^{26}Al gamma-ray line
- determined the Galactic cc-SN rate independently
- determined the $^{26}\text{Al}/^{60}\text{Fe}$ yield ratio constraining SN models
- monitored the past activity of Sgr A* via its Compton echo
- determined the hard X-ray luminosity function of AGN

What was predicted and not achieved ?

Search for historic supernovae

- Expect ~ 3 supernova/century in Galaxy with ^{44}Ti emission lines (98 y)
- $F(^{44}\text{Ti}) \sim 1,2 \times 10^{-4} e^{-(t/98 \text{ y})} \text{ ph cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} (\text{d}/10 \text{ kpc})^{-2}$
- Expect to detect, via Galactic Plane Scans, “hot spots” @ 68, 78, 1156 keV (^{44}Ti) from historic Galactic supernovae, i.e. 100 – 600 years ago from the entire Galaxy
- Insignificant point sources at other wavelengths (radio, IR, X, optical)
- Unique opportunity to directly measure the Galactic supernova rate

L.S. Thé et al. (2006) conclude that

- *Core collapse supernovae have been improbably **rare** in the Galaxy during the past few centuries,*
- or
- *The ^{44}Ti -producing supernovae are **atypical** supernovae.*

Murphy in space

In IBIS field of view ~ 10 GRB per y

In OMC field of view < 1 GRB per 2y?

Gamma-ray burst in 2005

Gamma-ray burst in 2009

What was not predicted ? The Unexpected

I GR sources: a new class of binaries

IAU Circular #8063
 Few months after launch

IGR J16318-4848

T. J.-L. Courvoisier, INTEGRAL Science Data Centre (ISDC), Versoix, writes that R. Walter, ISDC; J. Rodriguez, Centre d'Etude Atomique and Service d'Astrophysique, Saclay; L. Bouchet, Centre d'Etude Spatial du Rayonnement, Toulouse; and A. A. Lutovinov, Space Research Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow, report the detection of the first transient source observed by the ISGRI detector of the IBIS instrument onboard the European Space Agency's INTEGRAL satellite. The source appeared at R.A. = 16h31m52s, Decl. = -48o48'.5 (equinox 2000.0; uncertainty about 2'), while INTEGRAL was performing an observation of the Galactic plane on Jan. 29.271 UT. The source flux in the band 15-40 keV was 50-100 mCrab. The source was observed to vary significantly on a timescale of 1000 s. INTEGRAL will observe the source again during Feb. 1-3. Observations at other wavelengths are encouraged.

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2003 February 1

(8063)

Daniel W. E. Green

R. Walter et al., 2003

A. Bodaghee, 2011

Rare outburst from SGR 1806-20

SGR 1806-20 Outburst on December 27, 2004

Mereghetti et al., 2005

- “Soft gamma-repeater”
- Strongest gamma-flare ever!
- Disturbed Earth’ ionosphere
- Amount of energy emitted in first 0.2 s = solar output during 250.000 years

Earth occultation: the cosmic X-ray background

ISGRI, @30 keV

Instrumental background

CXB (sky) background

Celestial point sources

Earth emission

E. Churazov et al., 2007

GRB170817A = γ -ray counterpart of GW170817

Predicted by Einstein (General Relativity):

Acceleration of masses produces “ripples” in space-time \rightarrow “gravitational waves”

20 years INTEGRAL

Thank you for your attention

**Special thanks to the
Scientific Community
Space Agencies
Industry**

& last no least to the

- co-veterans
- soon - to - be veterans